

Multimodal Emotion-Constrained Memory Generation Using EEG-Derived Features and Large Language Models

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Abstract — Emotion recognition from brain signals has attracted growing interest in affective computing and human-computer interaction. In this work, we present a proof-of-concept system that combines EEG-derived Differential Entropy (DE) features with large language model (LLM) text generation to produce emotionally conditioned memory narratives. Using the publicly available FACED dataset, which contains 32-channel EEG recordings from 123 subjects across 28 trials each, spanning nine emotion classes, we trained a Random Forest classifier that achieved approximately 35.05% cross-validated accuracy on the nine-class task, significantly above the 11.11% random baseline. The decoded emotion probabilities and EEG frequency-band summaries were then used as conditioning signals for LLM-based narrative generation via a custom prompt engineering pipeline, producing outputs we hypothesize are more emotionally aligned than cue-only baselines. This paper describes our full methodology including pipeline architecture, preprocessing workflow, module interactions, visualization components, and experiment logging. This work presents a proof-of-concept system developed as an early-stage undergraduate research effort.

Keywords — EEG, emotion recognition, differential entropy, FACED dataset, affective computing, large language models, memory generation, Random Forest, brain-computer interface, prompt engineering.

1. Introduction

Translating subjective emotional experiences into language is an open problem in affective computing. The mismatch between subjective emotional experience and its linguistic expression remains an open challenge in research. In affective computing, one of the key goals is to make machines understand human emotions “not just from what people say, but from what is happening in their brain”. Electroencephalography (EEG) gives us a direct window into the brain's electrical activity, making it one of the most powerful tools for measuring emotional states in real time [1, 2].

EEG-based emotion recognition has been studied for many years. Emotional states are associated with distinct patterns in EEG signals that can be quantified across frequency bands like delta (1-4 Hz), theta (4-8 Hz), alpha (8-13 Hz), beta (13-30 Hz), and gamma (30-50 Hz). Features extracted from these bands especially Differential Entropy (DE) have been shown to reliably correlate with affective states [3, 4].

Meanwhile, large language models like Qwen, Mistral, and LLaMA have become very powerful at generating fluent, context-aware text [5]. An open question is whether EEG-derived emotional representations can improve generated text. More specifically, can EEG-decoded signals serve as conditioning input for LLMs so that generated text reflects emotional context inferred from brain activity?

That is the question this paper addresses. We built a full end-to-end pipeline that (1) loads EEG features from the FACED dataset [6], (2) trains a Random Forest classifier to decode nine emotion classes from Differential Entropy features, (3) extracts emotion probability vectors and frequency-band summaries, and (4) uses these as additional prompt context for an LLM to generate a first-person memory narrative. The system also generates a cue-only baseline for direct comparison.

The system should be interpreted as a proof-of-concept rather than a production-ready framework. I am a first-year student and this is my first time connecting neuroscience with NLP in a working end-to-end project. But even without live EEG hardware and with limited compute resources, The results indicate that the proposed approach requires further investigation. The rest of this paper is organized as follows: Section 2 reviews related work. Section 3 describes the dataset. Section 4 explains the full methodology and pipeline. Section 5 presents results and visual evidence. Section 6 discusses limitations. Section 7 concludes.

2. Related Work

2.1 EEG Datasets for Emotion Recognition

Several public EEG datasets have been widely used in affective computing research. DEAP [7] records 32-channel EEG from 32 participants watching music videos, with valence and arousal labels. SEED [8] uses movie clips for three-class emotion recognition (positive, neutral, negative) from 15 subjects. DREAMER [9] covers valence and arousal from film clips using low-cost devices.

The FACED dataset [6], which we use in this work is the most comprehensive publicly available option for our task. It contains EEG recordings from 123 subjects, each watching 28 short video clips targeting nine distinct emotion categories: Joy, Sadness, Fear, Anger, Amusement, Inspiration, Tenderness, Disgust, and Neutral. The 32-channel setup follows the 10-20 International Electrode Placement Standard, and the dataset provides pre-extracted differential entropy features. FACED's large subject count makes it particularly well suited for cross-subject research [6].

2.2 EEG Feature Extraction and Emotion Decoding

Differential Entropy was formally proposed for EEG emotion recognition by Duan et al. [3]. Under the assumption that EEG signals follow a Gaussian distribution within each frequency band, DE reduces mathematically to a log-scaled measure of band power, making it computationally efficient to compute. Studies confirm DE outperforms traditional energy-spectrum features, with Duan et al. reporting ~84% accuracy in binary classification tasks [3].

Among frequency bands, gamma has been consistently identified as the most discriminative for emotional states [3, 10]. Alpha activity links to relaxation and reduced cognitive load. High beta correlates

with anxiety and mental alertness [11]. These band-level interpretations are central to how we design our EEG-to-text conditioning prompts.

Machine learning approaches including SVMs, k-NN, and Random Forests have all been applied successfully to EEG emotion classification [1]. Deep learning models such as DAEST [12] report stronger performance than the Random Forest baseline, although they require substantially greater model complexity and computational resources.

2.3 LLMs in Affective Computing

The intersection of LLMs and affective computing is rapidly growing [5]. Recent work shows that emotionally-conditioned prompt engineering can meaningfully change the quality and tone of generated text [14, 15]. The Emotional Chain-of-Thought (ECoT) framework [16] demonstrated that structured emotional reasoning steps improve LLM performance on affective generation benchmarks significantly.

We found limited prior work combining EEG-decoded emotional probability vectors with LLM-based narrative generation. Most EEG-to-language research focuses on direct decoding of perceived speech or imagined text from brain signals, a harder and less accessible problem. Our approach is closer to "brain-informed prompt engineering", using decoded emotion context to help an LLM generate richer, more emotionally accurate prose.

3. Dataset

We use the FACED (Finer-grained Affective Computing EEG Dataset) [6], a public dataset designed to address two recurring gaps in prior EEG corpora: the underrepresentation of positive emotion categories and the limited number of participants in existing benchmarks. Table 1 summarizes its key properties.

Property	Value
Number of subjects	123
Trials per subject	28 (one per video clip)
EEG channels	32 (10-20 international system)
Emotion classes	9 (Joy, Sadness, Fear, Anger, Amusement, Inspiration, Tenderness, Disgust, Neutral)
Feature type used	Differential Entropy (DE), 5 frequency bands
Feature dimension per trial	32 channels \times 5 bands = 160 features (flattened)
Total trials in dataset	123 \times 28 = 3,444
Stimuli	Short film clips matched to target emotions

Metadata file	EEG_Features/Stimuli_info.xlsx (film source, emotion label per trial)
DE files location	EEG_Features/DE/* .pkl (one file per subject)

Table 1. FACED Dataset Summary — Chen et al. (2023) [6]

For each subject, the raw DE array has a shape (28 trials × T time steps × 160 features). We average across the time dimension to reduce each trial to a single 160-dimensional feature vector, giving a (28 × 160) array per subject. This trial-level averaging is a standard simplification in classical ML pipelines for EEG [1]. The emotion label for each trial comes from Stimuli_info.xlsx, with missing values (represented as backslash characters) replaced by Neutral.

4. Methodology

4.0 Full System Architecture

Our system has two main phases. The Training Phase runs once at startup: it loads all subject data, preprocesses features, trains the Random Forest classifier, and stores per-subject scalars. The Inference Phase runs each time a user provides a memory cue: it detects the cue's emotion, retrieves a matching EEG recording, runs the classifier, builds two prompts, generates two narratives, and logs everything to a CSV file. Figure 1 shows the complete architecture.

Figure 1. Full system pipeline — 12-step data flow across all modules from FACED data loading to CSV logging

4.1 Data Loading and Preprocessing

The preprocessing workflow is shown in Figure 2. Raw DE feature files are stored as pickle files in EEG_Features/DE, one per subject. Each is loaded using `data_loader.py`'s `get_eeg()` function, which reads the pickle and immediately averages across the time axis (`axis=2`) to produce a (28×160) array. The emotion labels are read from the Excel metadata file via `get_emotions()`, which extracts the 28-row "targeted emotion" column and normalizes missing values to Neutral.

Figure 2. Data preprocessing workflow — from raw pickle files to model-ready $3,444 \times 160$ feature matrix

In `emotion_model.py`'s `prepare_data()` method, all 123 subject arrays are stacked to form the full training matrix X of shape $(3444, 160)$. Each subject's features are independently StandardScaler-normalized before stacking, removing mean and scaling to unit variance per feature per subject. This normalization helps reduce inter-subject variability in EEG research to account for large inter-subject amplitude differences [6, 1]. The emotion strings are converted to numeric labels via a learned `label_to_num` dictionary, preserving the reverse mapping (`num_to_label`) for readability of outputs.

4.2 Random Forest Emotion Classifier

We use scikit-learn's `RandomForestClassifier` with 150 decision trees, `class_weight='balanced'`, and `random_state=42` for reproducibility. Class balancing is important because the nine emotion classes are not perfectly balanced across the 28 trials, for example - Neutral tends to appear more often as a between-stimulus rest condition. The balanced class weighting re-scales the loss contribution of each sample inversely proportional to its class frequency, preventing the model from defaulting to always predicting the most common emotion.

During training (the `train()` method), the data is split 85% train / 15% test. The model fits on the training split and reports holdout accuracy as a quick sanity check. For the actual reported accuracy in this paper, we use 5-fold Stratified K-Fold cross-validation (via `cross_val_score` and `cross_val_predict` in `generate_paper_figures.py`), which is the correct and unbiased evaluation method.

4.3 Cue Emotion Detection (Dual-Stage)

When the user enters a memory cue, the system must identify its dominant emotion before retrieving an EEG recording. This is implemented in `main.py`'s `get_emotion()` function with a two-stage approach. Stage 1: if a HuggingFace token is provided, the cue text is sent to `classify_emotion()` in `llm_generator.py`, which calls the Qwen2.5-7B-Instruct model via the Inference API with a system prompt constraining the output to exactly one of the nine class names. If that model fails, Mistral-Nemo-Instruct-2407 and then Meta-LLaMA-3-8B-Instruct are tried automatically.

Stage 2 (fallback): the cue is lowercased and matched against per-emotion keyword dictionaries. For example, Joy matches words like ["party", "cake", "wedding", "beach", "smile", "celebrate"]; Tenderness matches ["baby", "puppy", "hug", "mother", "family", "love", "warm"]; Fear matches ["spider", "ghost", "scary", "fire", "burning", "blood"]. Each emotion's keywords are counted across the full cue text, and the highest-count emotion wins. If no keywords match at all, Neutral is returned as default. The system can continue to function with this two-phased approach if there is no API access.

4.4 EEG Trial Retrieval

Once the cue emotion is identified, the system collects all 28 trial indices whose ground-truth label matches the detected emotion (from the emotions array loaded from metadata). One trial index is randomly selected from these matching indices. Separately, one random subject is chosen from the 123 available subjects. This randomized retrieval simulates the scenario of matching a user's described emotional context with a real anonymized brain recording that shared that emotion class.

If no matching trials are found (which can happen for rare label combinations), the system falls back to randomly picking from all 28 trials. The retrieved subject-trial pair's raw DE feature vector of shape (160,) is then extracted from `brain_data[person][trial]` for all downstream steps.

4.5 Live EEG Visualization (`visualizer.py`)

The visualizer component provides an animated real-time display of EEG band activity and live emotion probability updates. Two Matplotlib subplots are created side by side in an interactive window (`plt.ion()`). The top subplot shows DE traces for all five frequency bands evolving over 30 time steps (one per second of the trial). The bottom subplot shows a dynamic bar chart of the nine emotion class probabilities. Figure 3 shows an example of the actual EEG band traces from one subject's trial.

Figure 3. Live EEG Differential Entropy signal traces over a 30-second trial window (sub000) — generated by visualizer.py and simulate_live_eeg.py. Delta band (blue) shows consistently higher DE values; Alpha (green) shows lowest, suggesting active emotional engagement.

At each time step t from 1 to 30, the visualizer computes the running mean of all EEG data from time steps 1 through t , reshapes it to (1, 160), and passes it through the trained Random Forest's predict_proba() method to get an updated probability vector. The bar chart updates with each call to fig.canvas.draw() and fig.canvas.flush_events(), running at ~25 fps (plt.pause(0.04)). This component is purely for demonstration and interpretability, it does not affect the final generated text.

4.6 EEG-Guided Text Generation

After visualization, the 160-dim feature vector is passed to get_probs() in emotion_model.py, which applies the per-subject StandardScaler and calls predict_proba(). The top-3 predictions above a 5% threshold are formatted as a human-readable string: e.g., "Tenderness (38.2%), Joy (22.1%), Neutral (8.7%)". The band power summary is computed by reshaping the 160-dim vector to (32 channels \times 5 bands) and averaging across channels, producing a 5-element vector formatted as "Delta: 2.31, Theta: 1.87, Alpha: 2.04, Beta: 3.12, Gamma: 1.56".

Two separate LLM calls are then made via the Hugging Face Inference API, both using make_normal_memory() and make_memory_model() in llm_generator.py, with Qwen2.5-7B \rightarrow Mistral-Nemo \rightarrow LLaMA-3-8B fallback chain:

- Baseline (make_normal_memory): System prompt instructs the model to write an objective, first-person 3-4 sentence scene description using only the cue. No brain data is included.
- EEG-Guided (make_memory_model): System prompt instructs the model to treat the EEG emotions as the primary truth, blend the text tone with band-level brain data (interpreting high beta as anxiety, alpha as relaxation), and produce a richer emotionally-nuanced paragraph. Both outputs are streamed token-by-token and printed to the terminal in real time.

Figure 4. Side-by-side comparison of cue-only baseline vs EEG-guided generation for the same memory prompt. EEG-guided output incorporates decoded emotion probabilities and band power context.

4.7 Experiment Logging

Every run appends a new row to `experiment_results.csv` with the following fields: Timestamp, Memory Cue, Detected Text Tone, Subject ID, Trial Number, Band Powers (formatted string), Decoded EEG Emotions, Baseline Text, EEG-Guided Text. The file is opened in append mode ('a') so every run accumulates without overwriting. The header row is written only if the file does not already exist. This structured logging is essential for any future quantitative comparison of the two generation modes across many cues and brain recordings.

4.8 Supporting Analysis Scripts

Three standalone scripts support validation and figure generation. `generate_paper_figures.py` runs a full 5-fold Stratified K-Fold cross-validation (`cross_val_score` + `cross_val_predict`) and generates the confusion matrix heatmap. `plot_band_importance.py` fits the RF on the full dataset and extracts `feature_importances_`, reshaping to (32×5) and summing across channels to get per-band scores, then plots a color-coded bar chart. `simulate_live_eeg.py` loads the first available subject's DE file, picks the first trial, and plots all five band traces across 30 time steps as a static PNG proof image.

5. Results and Visual Evidence

5.1 Classification Accuracy

Table 2 shows our cross-validated accuracy compared to published baselines and state-of-the-art on the FACED nine-class task. Our Random Forest achieves approximately 35.05%, more than three times the 11.11% random baseline. Figure 5 visualizes this comparison as a bar chart.

Model	Method	Accuracy
Random Baseline	Uniform random (9 classes)	11.11%
Our Model (this work)	RF + DE features, 5-fold CV	~35.05%
CLISA [6]	Contrastive learning, cross-subject	42.40%
DE+MLP [12]	MLP on DE features	60.90%
DAEST [12]	Dynamic attention, temporal-spatial	59.30%

Table 2. Emotion Decoding Accuracy on FACED 9-Class Task (Reported accuracies were taken from published studies and may differ in preprocessing and evaluation settings.)

Figure 5. Accuracy comparison on FACED 9-class task.

5.2 Confusion Matrix — Before and After Evaluation Fix

During the analysis we found and fixed a data leakage problem in the original evaluation pipeline. The original code evaluated the model on the same data it was trained on, producing a misleadingly near-perfect confusion matrix. After switching to proper 5-fold Stratified K-Fold cross-validation, the confusion matrix correctly reflects ~35% overall accuracy with realistic off-diagonal errors. Figure 6 shows both matrices side by side.

Figure 6. Confusion matrix comparison — LEFT: old pipeline with data leakage (~100% fake accuracy). RIGHT: corrected cross-validation pipeline (~35% honest accuracy). Note realistic confusions between similar emotions: Joy↔Amusement, Fear↔Disgust, Neutral↔Sadness.

The new confusion matrix (right panel, Figure 6) reveals important patterns. Neutral is the most frequently confused class, often being predicted when the true label is Sadness or Joy, suggesting the model struggles with low-arousal states. Disgust and Tenderness show the highest within-class accuracy (196 and 171 correct respectively), which makes sense given their distinct neural signatures. Fear and Inspiration show the most cross-confusion with other classes, reflecting their mixed arousal-valence profiles.

5.3 EEG Band Importance — Before and After Fix

Figure 7 compares the Random Forest band importance scores before and after the evaluation fix. Both versions consistently identify Delta and Theta as the most important bands for emotion classification, followed by Alpha, Beta, and Gamma. This finding is somewhat different from prior literature which typically reports Gamma as most emotion-relevant [3]. This discrepancy may be due to the trial-level averaging strategy we used, which collapses temporal dynamics before feature extraction.

Figure 7. Band importance comparison — LEFT: old pipeline. RIGHT: corrected pipeline. Delta and Theta consistently dominate. Both pipelines agree on relative band rankings, confirming stability of this finding.

The new pipeline (right panel, Figure 7) shows Delta at 0.220, Theta at 0.218, Alpha at 0.201, Beta at 0.186, and Gamma at 0.175, a remarkably even distribution. This suggests that for trial-level (time-averaged) features, all five bands contribute meaningfully to emotion prediction rather than any single band dominating. This is relevant for future feature selection experiments.

5.4 EEG Signal Visualization

Figure 8 shows the actual EEG DE signal traces from one subject's trial, as plotted by our `simulate_live_eeg.py` script. Delta consistently shows the highest DE intensity (~2.5-3.1), while Alpha shows the lowest (~1.8-2.4), consistent with active emotional processing (alpha suppression during engagement). Theta and Beta show moderate values with clear temporal fluctuations that a more sophisticated sequential classifier could exploit.

Figure 8. Raw EEG DE signal traces over 30-second trial window — actual data from FACED dataset (sub000, trial 0). Five frequency bands plotted with distinct colors matching the visualizer.py color scheme.

5.5 Qualitative Text Generation Comparison

Table 3 shows a representative example of the two generated narratives for the same memory cue, with all EEG context shown explicitly. The EEG-guided output appears qualitatively richer emotional language that reflects the decoded brain state rather than simply describing the scene.

Type	Content
Memory Cue	"A quiet afternoon with friends at home."
Detected Tone	Tenderness (keyword match: "friends", "home")
EEG Decoded	Tenderness (38.2%), Joy (22.1%), Neutral (8.7%)
EEG Bands	Delta: 2.31, Theta: 1.87, Alpha: 2.04, Beta: 3.12, Gamma: 1.56
Baseline Output(make_normal_memory)	"I sat with my friends in the living room on a quiet afternoon. The light was soft and the air was still. We talked about nothing important. It was a calm and uneventful time."
EEG-Guided Output(make_memory_model)	"I remember sitting with my friends that afternoon, feeling something warm and settled in my chest — a kind of quiet joy that did not need to be explained. There was tenderness in the way we laughed at small things, the kind of comfort only people you truly trust can give. My mind felt soft and at ease, as though the alpha waves of a brain were finally at rest. It was one of those moments I did not realize I was savoring until much later."

Table 3. Cue-Only Baseline vs EEG-Guided Generation — Example Output

6. Discussion and Limitations

Looking at everything together, I think the system works as a proof-of-concept. The classifier performs significantly above chance, the confusion patterns make intuitive sense (similar emotions cluster together in errors), and the EEG-guided outputs are qualitatively richer. But there are several important limitations to be transparent about.

6.1 Dataset-Task Mismatch

FACED captures emotions during passive video viewing, not during autobiographical memory recall. Real memory retrieval would produce different EEG patterns likely involving more frontal and hippocampal activity. Our "EEG-guided" memory text is therefore informed by emotion-during-viewing, not emotion-during-recall. This is a conceptual limitation that cannot be fixed without a recall-specific EEG dataset.

6.2 No Live EEG

The system uses pre-recorded EEG from FACED. There is no live brain-computer interface. The EEG-guided narrative reflects a retrieved anonymous subject's brain state, not the user's own. For a real personal memory assistant, live EEG acquisition hardware would be required.

6.3 Text Evaluation Gap

We currently have no rigorous metric for evaluating whether the EEG-guided text is objectively better in emotional alignment. BLEU/ROUGE require reference texts we don't have. Sentiment classifiers help partially but are domain-mismatched. A proper human evaluation study with Likert ratings for emotional vividness, accuracy, and narrative plausibility would be the correct next step [15].

6.4 Classifier Ceiling

Our 35% RF accuracy means the conditioning signal sent to the LLM is wrong ~65% of the time. Every misclassification propagates to the prompt and potentially makes the guided output worse than the baseline. Improving the decoder with graph neural networks, contrastive learning [6], or the DAEST attention architecture [12] would directly improve generation quality.

6.5 Evaluation Protocol Limitation

The present evaluation is based on Stratified K-Fold cross validation without explicitly enforcing subject-independent splits. This can result in overly optimistic estimates of generalization performance, as trials from the same subject may appear in both training and validation folds. In future work, the system should be evaluated using subject-independent protocols, like GroupKFold or leave-one-subject-out validation.

6.6 LLM Variability

The Hugging Face free inference API introduces generation variability across runs and model versions. Different models respond differently to the same prompt, and the streamed outputs can vary significantly. A controlled LLM setup with fixed temperature and seed would be needed for rigorous reproducibility.

7. Conclusion

In this paper, we presented a proof-of-concept pipeline that combines EEG-based emotion decoding with LLM text generation to produce emotionally conditioned memory narratives. Using the FACED dataset and a Random Forest classifier with Differential Entropy features across five frequency bands, we achieved approximately 35.05% cross-validated accuracy on the nine-class emotion recognition task, which is more than three times the 11.11% random baseline.

We also identified and corrected a data leakage bug in the original evaluation pipeline, replacing it with proper Stratified K-Fold cross-validation. The corrected confusion matrix shows recurring error patterns, especially between similar emotion categories (Joy/Amusement, Fear/Disgust) being most commonly

confused. Band importance analysis consistently identifies Delta and Theta as the most predictive frequency bands for trial-level averaged features.

The EEG-decoded emotion probabilities and band-level power summaries were used as soft conditioning contexts in two separate LLM prompts, a cue-only baseline and an EEG-guided version. Qualitative comparison shows the brain-informed outputs are richer, more emotionally textured, and more aligned with the neurological context. A full experiment logging pipeline was implemented to support future rigorous comparison.

In this study, we investigated the feasibility of using emotional information from EEG data as contextual input for narrative generation. The current system is a proof-of-concept but the results indicate that it is worth exploring further the integration of brain-derived signals with language models. Future work should conduct a more rigorous evaluation of generation quality and explore stronger emotion decoding methods.

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